

REMOTE COLLABORATION MADE EASY WITH XR

We aim to facilitate remote collaboration between workers through next-generation extended reality (XR) technology solutions across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

The highly innovative XR platform we are developing will facilitate work and social activities involving physical interaction with the environment and remote objects — from industrial cooperation to technical training and business meetings.

CORTEX²

WE ARE LOOKING FOR INNOVATORS TO CREATE THE NEXT GENERATION OF XR TECHNOLOGIES

We will invest €4 million in 2 open calls to recruit and support 30 European SMEs and industry actors — from research-oriented institutions to business-driven organisations — in the co-development of our CORTEX² platform and its replication in different domains.

2

OPEN CALLS

30

IDEAS

€4

MILLION

Watch out for our next open call for 2023!

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